

METROLOGICAL SUPPORT IN PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT

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***Abstract.** This article examines general information on quality management, quality assessment for metrological support purposes, and formulas for determining quality indicators.*

***Keywords:** quality management, quality, requirements, metrological support.*

INTRODUCTION

Quality management affects the economic efficiency of an enterprise and organization's operations both in the short and long term. Some short-term improvements can have negative long-term consequences, contributing to the formation of an unfavorable opinion about the enterprise's products. Control and management of product quality enables solving current and future tasks and, most importantly, increasing its competitiveness.

The need to produce high-quality products that meet modern market requirements necessitates addressing the following tasks:

- production of new products that meet the highest global standards;
- achievement of product quality requirements;
- mandatory control of the technical level and quality of the manufacturing enterprise's products, taking into account consumer requirements;
- maintaining the required level of metrological support for production and technological processes;
- a comprehensive approach to product quality control and management [1,2].

To improve product quality, as well as production effectiveness and efficiency, information on the parameters of tested products is essential. This information serves as the basis for assessing the product's compliance with established regulatory requirements.

To obtain information about product quality, it is necessary to monitor testing procedures, taking into account their relationship with measurements. Ensuring the necessary accuracy, correctness, and reliability of measurements is only possible by establishing an optimal metrological support system within the enterprise or organization. Measurements, as an object of metrological support, accompany the entire life cycle of a product, work, or service. The qualitative characteristics of measurement results are particularly important when assessing product quality prior to transferring goods from the manufacturer to the end consumer[3].

MATERIALS, METHODS AND RESULTS

Product quality assessment refers to the evaluation of quantitative measurement results. This task is addressed by the science of qualimetry. The consequences of ineffective quality management due to unreliable assessment in modern conditions are very serious. It is important to correctly determine the level of product quality during its certification, planning, and forecasting

of quality improvement at all stages of the life cycle. In metrology support practice, it is advisable to apply quality assessment procedures when developing new measurement systems, evaluating the state of metrological support for measurements, and improving the overall metrological support of an enterprise. Examples of analyzed product types in metrological practice can include measuring instruments, measurement complexes including their software, and measurement technologies (methods for measurement, control, verification, calibration, etc.).

Assessment of product quality consists of three main stages:

- 1) selecting the nomenclature of quality indicators;
- 2) determining the values of these indicators for the evaluated product;
- 3) comparing the obtained values with the baseline values.

In general, it is necessary to:

- formulate the purpose of the assessment (for example, establish the level of metrological characteristics of the analyzed measuring equipment);
- clarify the assessment conditions;
- decide on the required accuracy of the assessment result;
- select and justify the necessary and sufficient number of indicators that establish the quality of the evaluated product;
- Select a base sample (reference sample) of the product, including assigning justified values for its quality indicators; choose analysis or testing methods to determine the actual values of quality indicators;
- Obtain and process the necessary experimental data, ensuring its representativeness;
- Compare the quality characteristics of the evaluated product with those of the base sample;
- Obtain a comparison result;
- Make a decision.

The specific content and number of assessment stages depend on its purpose and the task constraints.

Depending on the purpose of assessing the product quality level, three types of base samples are used:

- Those reflecting prospective requirements;
- Those reflecting international quality requirements;
- Those reflecting the requirements of national regulatory documents[4].

Before assigning quality requirements for the base sample corresponding to one of the specified types, a set of quality indicators necessary and sufficient for subsequent assessment is determined.

Quality indicators can be divided into indicators of purpose, manufacturability, safety, environmental impact, preservation, and patent law compliance. Regarding manufacturability indicators, there is a procedure that involves obtaining the result of dividing the total costs attributed to a certain period by the quantity of products manufactured during that same period.

For performance indicators, average arithmetic values for a month, quarter, or year are specified. If the entire sum of costs relative to the total mass of manufactured products is used to determine technological indicators, then for performance indicators, data from "point" measurements are averaged without considering batch mass. More reliable than arithmetic means are the mass-weighted average values of the i -th quality indicator P_i

$$P_i = \frac{\sum m_k P_i}{\sum mk}, \quad (1)$$

where k are the sequential numbers of product batches produced during the evaluated time period; mk is the mass of the batch with sequential number k .

In addition to accounting for batch mass, a sufficiently large data sample is needed to ensure the reliability of the product quality characteristic (for example, all or at least 100 values taken at equal time intervals throughout the entire evaluated period).

However, the mass-weighted average does not indicate the stability of a qualitative characteristic, and the need to assess stability arises quite often. Therefore, the complete characterization of the product's quality indicator consists of the given value P_i , which includes in the numerator the mass-weighted average P_{ic} and the scatter of indicator values in the denominator. In this case, if the standard in the technical documentation is set as "not less than" or "not more than," then

$$\Pi_i = \frac{P_{ic}}{P_{\min} \div P_{i\max}}; \quad (2)$$

if the standard is given as "within limits," then

$$\Pi_i = \frac{\Delta_{jc}}{\Delta_{j\min} \div \Delta_{j\max}}, \quad (3)$$

where $P_{i\min}$, $P_{i\max}$ are the lower and upper limits of the actual values of the i th indicator; $\Delta_{i\min}$, $\Delta_{i\max}$

are the lower and upper boundaries of the actual intervals of values for the i th indicator, taken after excluding 5% of the largest and 5% of the smallest values.

Exclusion of 5% of extreme values is done to ensure better comparability of the given characteristics of products from different enterprises: the data intervals $P_{i\min} - P_{i\max}$ and $\Delta_{j\min} - \Delta_{j\max}$ do not include values related to rare (one-time) events (deviations during the technological process of product manufacturing). For statistical calculation of actual value intervals of P_i and Δ_j for products, initial data are usually not suitable due to their insignificant variation from the average.

In addition to the indicators of purpose and manufacturability, it is advisable to determine the indicators of product preservation. To substantiate this complex property, experimental data are required, obtained under conditions as close as possible to those established in the technical documentation for the products, and in a quantity sufficient to ensure a certain level of reliability of obligations (since the preservation indicator in the technical documentation

is guaranteed, and its actual values vary randomly from batch to batch).

Experimental data are obtained at manufacturing enterprises, where, in accordance with the instructions of the "Product Storage" section of the technical documentation, representative samples of manufactured products (taken from batches that meet the quality requirements of the technical documentation and obtained with full compliance with the production technological regulations) are submitted for testing, and their quality indicators are periodically determined.

If all quality indicators remain at their initial values for an extended period (1-2 years), the product is classified as stable during storage, and its warranty period is set equal to the total duration of testing. If, over time, the values of one or more quality indicators deteriorate, then the

accumulation of experimental data ceases when the indicator values fall outside the requirements of the Scientific and Technical Documentation (STD). The time period during which the value of a quality indicator remains within the STD requirements is called the permissible storage time for the k -th indicator of the n -th product sample. The total number of values is equal to the product of the number of tested product samples and the number of quality indicators being studied. The guaranteed shelf life t_g specified in the STD represents, in the case under consideration, a given 80% shelf life with an 80% confidence probability, obtained from the ratio

$$t_r = kt_{don}^{\min} \quad (4)$$

Where t_{perm} is the lowest value from the obtained data set; k is a statistical coefficient dependent on the number of samples, the given probability and confidence probability, which, as indicated above, are taken as equal to 80%; k_1 and depends on the number of tested product samples.

It should be noted that if the product manufacturing technology or the set of quality indicators in the technical documentation changes, new experimental data must be obtained to establish the warranty shelf life. The approximate warranty shelf life for new products is determined based on accelerated testing data. The principle of these tests, widely used for chemical products and their formulations, involves increasing the storage temperature of samples, which, according to the well-known Arrhenius law, doubles the rate of all chemical reactions for every ten-degree increase (including those that lead to changes in quality indicator values).

When assessing product quality, one of the most crucial stages is selecting the reference sample. A reference sample is a product that corresponds to advanced scientific and technological achievements for a specified period. The definition implies that to establish a reference sample (and its quality requirements), reliable and comprehensive information about all analogues of the evaluated product is necessary. Product analogues should include items with the same purpose (used to satisfy the same needs) and manufactured on an industrial scale.

Depending on the purpose of assessing product quality levels, three types of reference samples are used: those reflecting prospective requirements, those reflecting international quality requirements, and those reflecting requirements of national regulatory documents. Before establishing quality requirements for the reference sample corresponding to one of the specified types, a set of quality indicators necessary and sufficient for subsequent assessment is determined.

The task of accurately describing product quality typically requires quite complex work. The properties characterizing the quality of the evaluated object are not a simple set, but an ordered collection, a hierarchical structure ("property tree").

Having information about analogues and constructing a property tree characterizing quality, one proceeds to establish requirements for the reference sample. In doing so, it is not permitted to create a hypothetical (unrealizable) set of requirements. Characteristics of an analogue can serve as a reference sample if all of them are planned (for prospective assessment) or implemented (for current assessment) in a specific analogue.

The procedure for determining the reference sample must be performed using the expert method, which is an approach to problem-solving where a group of people competent in the discussed issue (experts) participates, providing new information, not using the same solution algorithm for everyone, and relying on their own experience and intuition rather than on data from calculations and experiments.

Next, the product indicators are compared with those of the base sample. In its most comprehensive form, this operation involves comparing the integral quality of the product I and the base sample I_0 . Integral quality is the totality of all properties of an object selected for evaluation. These properties are represented by corresponding absolute indicators that differ from each other in scales of various dimensions. Therefore, absolute indicators are not directly comparable, and in the quality assessment procedure, relative indicators are first determined:

$$q_i = \frac{P_i}{P_{i0}} \quad (5)$$

$$q_j = \frac{P_{j0}}{P_j} \quad (6)$$

where the index "b" refers to the base sample, and P_i, P_j can be limit values

P_{pr} (P_{imin}, P_{imax} OR P_{jmin}, P_{jmax}) OR weighted averages (P_{iavg}, P_{javg}).

In accordance with the general rules for constructing relative indicators for quality assessment, from formulas (6) and (7), the one is selected where an increase in the relative value of the indicator corresponds to an improvement in product quality: when the standard for the indicator is expressed by a number with the words "not less than," formula (6) should be used, and with the words

"not more than," formula (7) should be used. Depending on how the quality indicators of the base sample are presented, the following types of relative indicators are obtained:

when absolute indicators are given by the standards "not less than" or "not more than," i.e., they have the form of standard norms

$$q_{i\min} = \frac{P_{i\min}}{P_{i0.np}} \quad \text{OR} \quad \frac{P_{i\min}}{P_{i0.np}} \quad (7)$$

when the base sample standards are given by the actual characteristics of type (2) or (3)

$$\frac{P_{i\min}}{P_{i0.np}} \quad \text{OR} \quad \frac{P_{i0.c}}{P_{i0.c}} \quad (8)$$

In cases where absolute indicators do not have quantitative norms (for example, ergonomics of measuring equipment), it is provided to determine a relative indicator q , reflecting three quality gradations: 1.00 corresponds to the expert conclusion that the quality of the base sample object is the same; 1.05 - the quality of the object is better; 0.95 - the quality of the object is worse. The comparison result can be obtained by differential, complex, or mixed methods.

When using the differential method (relative indicators method), the expert group considers all the relative indicators selected for evaluating the product's properties. If all relative indicator values are greater than or equal to 1.00, the product quality level is higher than or equal to the base sample level; if all indicators are less than 1.00 (or at least one is less than 1.00 and the others are equal to 1.00), the product quality level is lower than the base sample.

In all other variants of the obtained set of relative indicators, it is necessary to apply a comprehensive evaluation method that provides for the "consolidation" of the set of relative property indicators into a function $K=f(q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n)$, where most often the function represents a weighted average (arithmetic or geometric) value. The preference for one or another type of

function has not yet been proven. In the practice of assessing product quality, the weighted arithmetic mean indicator

$$K = \sum q_i a_i, \sum a_i = 1 \quad (9)$$

where a_i is the weight coefficient of the i th quality indicator.

Weight coefficients a_i should be determined by expert methods when developing products, with mandatory participation of the customer (or main consumer). The quality level of the evaluated product is higher than or equal to the level of the base sample if $K \geq 1.00$, and lower than the base sample if $K < 1.00$. A comprehensive method for assessing the level of product quality becomes unsuitable when it is difficult to combine all the relative indicators taken for evaluation (for example, purpose indicators and patent-legal indicators) into one generalizing indicator. In such cases, all combinable indicators are "rolled up" into a complex one, while for non-combinable indicators, relative indicators q_i are found separately for each. Then, the expert commission considers the complex and relative indicators as a whole and makes a decision based on this set. When information about the main quality indicator (reflecting the specific consumer effect) or, even better, an integral quality indicator (for example, the accuracy class of a measuring instrument) is available, the evaluation of the product is more reliable than using the methods considered above. When assessing the export potential of a product, it is necessary to determine its patent-legal indicators (patent protection and patent purity). For products, the object of inspection is the methods for determining quality indicators.

The consumer value of products includes environmental indicators (e.g., hazard class) and safety indicators (e.g., fire and explosion hazard). In metrological practice, it is advisable to also use ergonomic indicators for evaluation [5].

Conclusion

Thus, this article has examined the procedure for conducting quality assessment to achieve metrological support objectives. Determining the main quality indicators will allow for more effective implementation of necessary improvements in production, rational use of resources, as well as increasing the degree of compliance of finished products with the requirements set for them.

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